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MODELLING OF HARDWARE ACCELERATORS IN THE CLOUD- EDGE CONTINUUM WITH FEDERATED LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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Modelling of hardware accelerators in the cloud-edge
continuum with federated learning techniques

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RESUMEN

Introducción

El despliegue de nodos de cómputo basados en *Field Programmable Gate Arrays* (FPGA) en las infraestructuras de procesamiento conocidas como *edge-cloud* continuo mejora la eficiencia computacional y el ahorro energético en comparación con el uso de CPUs y las GPUs, al integrar aceleradores especializados con procesadores de propósito general, lo que ofrece una gran flexibilidad y rendimiento. Sin embargo, también plantean retos en la gestión de la carga de trabajo, ya que las tareas llegan de forma dinámica y no pueden optimizarse en tiempo de diseño. Para abordar esta cuestión, las infraestructuras de gestión de recursos deben adaptar los modelos en tiempo real, al tiempo que realizan un seguimiento tanto de las tareas como de las características de los nodos.

Este trabajo forma parte del proyecto de investigación europeo MYRTUS, cuyo objetivo es desarrollar un marco conceptual para la computación continua que integre a la perfección los recursos del *cloud*, el *fog* y el *edge*. El marco combina un motor impulsado por IA para optimizar el rendimiento, la eficiencia energética y la seguridad, con un entorno de diseño unificado para el modelado entre capas, el análisis y la generación automatizada de código.

MYRTUS se centra en la computación reconfigurable — sistemas, a menudo basados en FPGA, que pueden adaptar dinámicamente su hardware a cargas de trabajo específicas mediante una reconfiguración dinámica o parcial — y en el *cloud-edge* continuo, que permite un despliegue flexible de aplicaciones en *clouds* centralizadas y dispositivos periféricos distribuidos. Este enfoque permite un procesamiento de baja latencia, la toma de decisiones en tiempo real y un rendimiento, un consumo energético y una capacidad de respuesta optimizados en todo el espectro informático.

Juan Encinas et al. (2025) propusieron un enfoque de aprendizaje incremental utilizando árboles de regresión adaptativa de Hoeffding (del inglés, HART) para predecir la potencia y el rendimiento de aceleradores desplegados sobre FPGAs dinámicamente reconfigurables en este tipo de escenarios, lo que garantiza una baja sobrecarga de tiempo de ejecución, pero requiere un reentrenamiento frecuente en dispositivos individuales. Este trabajo de fin de master toma como punto de partida esa publicación y explora modelos alternativos de aprendizaje automático dentro de un marco de Aprendizaje Federado (del inglés, FL). El FL permite a los dispositivos (clientes) mejorar de forma colaborativa los modelos en diferentes plataformas sin compartir datos brutos, lo que reduce la frecuencia de reentrenamiento y promueve la transferencia de conocimientos entre los nodos.

Los objetivos principales del trabajo son:

1. Evaluar las arquitecturas de aprendizaje automático adecuadas para la integración de FL.
2. Analizar diferentes estrategias de agregación de FL.
3. Simular el FL con cargas de trabajo de clientes heterogéneas y evaluar el comportamiento a nivel de sistema.

Metodología

El marco propuesto en esta tesis se implementó íntegramente en Python, utilizando dos bibliotecas clave: Keras, para construir, entrenar y evaluar modelos de *Deep Learning* (DL), y Flower, para simular entornos de FL. El flujo de trabajo se dividió en dos etapas

principales. En la primera etapa, se estudiaron y optimizaron diferentes modelos de *machine learning* con potencial para la integración en algoritmos de FL. Esto se logró mediante procedimientos de *grid-search*, en los que los modelos se entrenaron de forma incremental y se analizó su rendimiento utilizando diagramas de frontera de Pareto para equilibrar el error de predicción y el coste computacional. Una vez identificadas las arquitecturas más eficaces, la segunda etapa consistió en implementar un programa de FL que entrenó a tres clientes distribuidos, donde cada cliente representa el modelo desplegado en una FPGA. En esta fase, se probó una amplia gama de estrategias de agregación y se evaluó su rendimiento para determinar los enfoques más adecuados para la predicción dinámica de la carga de trabajo.

Se investigaron en detalle tres familias de modelos: Modelos basados en Funciones de Regresión utilizando un optimizador de Evolución diferencial autoadaptativa (del inglés, SaDE), Redes neuronales densas (del inglés, DNN) y Redes de memoria a corto y largo plazo (del inglés, LSTM). Se estudiaron tres funciones de regresión: función Linear, función de Rosenbrock y función de Rastrigin. SaDE es una variante de la optimización evolutiva clásica que integra parámetros de control adaptativo y selección probabilística de estrategias de mutación para mejorar la robustez. Su punto fuerte radica en la reducción del ajuste manual de parámetros y la adaptación dinámica al rendimiento histórico. En este trabajo, se empleó SaDE utilizando múltiples estrategias de mutación y cruce.

Se exploraron las DNN como una alternativa más escalable. Estas arquitecturas de alimentación directa se probaron en dos configuraciones: modelos de dos capas y de tres capas. Se llevó a cabo un procedimiento *grid-search*, variando el número de neuronas en cada capa y los tamaños de los lotes durante el entrenamiento.

La tercera familia de modelos estudiados fueron las LSTM, redes neuronales recurrentes diseñadas específicamente para capturar las dependencias temporales en datos secuenciales. Las células LSTM incorporan puertas de olvido, entrada y salida para regular el flujo de información y mitigar el problema del gradiente de desaparición. Se probaron varias variantes, incluyendo capas LSTM puras, LSTM con una o dos capas densas adicionales y configuraciones híbridas que combinaban una capa convolucional unidimensional con LSTM. Al igual que con las DNN, se realizó un procedimiento *grid-search* de hiperparámetros como el número de células, los tamaños de las capas densas, los tamaños de los núcleos y los tamaños de los lotes.

La evaluación de todos los modelos se basó en cinco métricas clave: error medio de predicción, desviación estándar del error, desviación media del error, tiempo de inferencia por punto de datos y tiempo total de entrenamiento. Estas métricas se visualizaron mediante diagramas de frontera de Pareto, lo que permitió una evaluación multidimensional del rendimiento de cada modelo. La compensación más crítica consistió en minimizar el error medio manteniendo un tiempo computacional total aceptable. Este enfoque garantizó que la selección del modelo se basara no solo en la precisión, sino también en limitaciones prácticas, como la eficiencia del tiempo de ejecución.

Una vez identificados los modelos con mejor rendimiento, la tesis avanzó a la etapa de FL. La base de datos de *Federated Learning* se subdividió en tres cargas de trabajo independientes, una por cliente, de modo que cada FPGA es capaz de considerar y adaptarse a las distintas características de las distribuciones de datos subyacentes. Posteriormente, los tres modelos se integra en un solo modelo en el servidor, el cual congrega las características todos ellos. Una valoración cruzada de 10 pliegues se ejecutó en cada carga de trabajo, entrenando cada cliente en 9 pliegues de su respectiva carga,

mientras que tanto los clientes como el servidor se evaluaron utilizando un conjunto de evaluación unificado compuesto por el pliegue restante de cada cliente.

Se estudiaron un total de doce estrategias de agregación para evaluar su eficacia en condiciones heterogéneas. El algoritmo de referencia, *FedAvg*, realizaba un simple promedio ponderado de las actualizaciones de los clientes, pero se sabe que es sensible a los datos no independientes e idénticamente distribuidos (*non-IID*) y los ataques bizantinos. Para abordar estas limitaciones, se probaron métodos de optimización adaptativa como *FedAdagrad*, *FedAdam* y *FedYogi*, cada uno de los cuales incorporaba diferentes estrategias para ajustar las tasas de aprendizaje y estabilizar la convergencia. Los enfoques basados en el impulso, como *FedAvgM* y el marco más general *FedOpt*, introdujeron optimizadores del lado del servidor para mejorar aún más la dinámica del entrenamiento. Se examinaron técnicas de agregación robustas, como *FedMedian*, *FedTrimmedAvg*, *Krum/Multi-Krum*, *Fault-Tolerant-FedAvg* y *Bulyan*, para determinar su capacidad de mitigar los efectos de los clientes bizantinos o los valores atípicos. Por último, se evaluó *FedProx* como método para estabilizar el entrenamiento con datos heterogéneos, penalizando las actualizaciones que se desvían significativamente del modelo global.

Resultados

Los modelos basados en funciones de regresión demostraron una capacidad predictiva deficiente, con errores porcentuales absolutos medios (MAPE) que superaban constantemente los umbrales aceptables. Su naturaleza estocástica y su sensibilidad al ajuste de parámetros lo hacían poco fiable para la predicción dinámica de la carga de trabajo. Del mismo modo, las LSTMs, a pesar de su capacidad teórica para captar las dependencias secuenciales, producían resultados inestables y mayores desviaciones de error. Su sobrecarga computacional limitaba aún más su idoneidad para su implementación en sistemas basados en FPGA.

Por el contrario, las DNNs se revelaron como la solución más eficaz. Tanto las arquitecturas de dos capas como las de tres capas, lograron sistemáticamente tasas de error más bajas, especialmente en las tareas de predicción de potencia, con un MAPE a menudo inferior al 5%. Es importante destacar que las DNNs de dos capas superaron a las más profundas, equilibrando la precisión predictiva con tiempos de entrenamiento e inferencia reducidos, como se presenta en la Tabla resumen 1 a continuación. Esta eficiencia las convirtió en candidatas ideales para su integración en simulaciones de FL. Aunque las DNNs no siempre superaron a los modelos originales de árboles de regresión, la capacidad de aplicar FL en ellas compensó ese hecho.

Tabla resumen 1: Mejores resultados usando DNNs

	Model	Mean error (%)	Sdv error (%)	Mean Error Dev. (%)	Total train time (s)	Individual infer time (s)
Top Power	FL 36 SL 24 BS 50	4.314	3.434	0.081	3.467	0.694
	FL 35 SL 25 TL 10 BS 25	4.089	3.266	0.066	4.690	0.755
	Modelo de Referencia HART	2.772	4.681	0.1331	28.088	0.027
Bottom Power	FL 24 SL 8 BS 25	3.876	3.458	0.575	4.354	0.745
	FL 30 SL 30 TL 10 BS 25	3.325	3.162	0.040	6.240	0.983
	Modelo de Referencia HART	2.017	3.952	0.2202	28.56	0.024
Time	FL 32 SL 12 BS 1	27.579	28.957	0.219	93.778	0.798
	FL 35 SL 25 TL 10 BS 1	26.695	27.934	0.565	130.844	1.035
	Modelo de Referencia HART	27.076	40.301	3.818	404.147	0.108

Note: FL = Primera capa, SL = Segunda capa, TL = Tercera capa, BS = Tamaño de lote; Los mejores resultados están resaltados en verde

En la segunda fase de los experimentos se evaluaron doce estrategias de agregación utilizando la base de datos Federated Learning, con tres clientes entrenados bajo particiones de carga de trabajo heterogéneas. Los modelos de cada cliente se actualizaron de forma incremental, se agregaron en el servidor y, a continuación, se evaluaron con un conjunto de validación combinado.

Los resultados mostraron que dos de las tres métricas (desviación estándar del error y tiempo consumido por paso de agregación) eran insignificantes en comparación con el error medio de la prueba. Además, se demostró la excepcional eficacia de estrategias específicas en función de la variable de salida. Para la predicción de la potencia de la CPU (*Top Power*), *FedMedian* ofreció el mejor rendimiento, mientras que para la predicción de la potencia de la FPGA (*Bottom Power*), *FedProx1* demostró ser la más robusta, gestionando eficazmente la heterogeneidad de la carga de trabajo. En cuanto al tiempo de ejecución, *Bulyan* superó sistemáticamente a otras estrategias.

Conclusiones y líneas de trabajo futuras

Los experimentos confirmaron la utilidad de las DNNs para la inferencia del sistema, con arquitecturas de dos capas que funcionaban mejor que las de tres capas, al tener menores tiempos de entrenamiento e inferencia, aunque con un ligero aumento del error. Se descubrió que el tamaño de lote (*batch size*) 1 solo era práctico para los modelos de tiempo de ejecución, ya que provocaba tiempos de entrenamiento excesivos para los modelos de potencia. Aunque la precisión general era ligeramente inferior a la del modelo de referencia utilizado anteriormente, la capacidad de integrar el FL compensaba esta diferencia.

Los resultados de la estrategia de aprendizaje federado mostraron que el tiempo de agregación era insignificante y que las diferencias entre estrategias eran mínimas. La variabilidad entre ejecuciones también fue insignificante para los modelos de potencia de CPU y FPGA, aunque era más notable para el de tiempo de ejecución. Según la evaluación, las estrategias más eficaces identificadas fueron *FedMedian* para los modelos de potencia de CPU, *FedProx1* para los modelos de potencia de FPGA y *Bulyan* para los modelos de tiempo de ejecución.

Por último, este trabajo sugiere varias vías para futuras investigaciones. En primer lugar, los resultados de nuestro marco podrían aplicarse a otras estrategias de FL, además de las ya codificadas en *Flower*. En segundo lugar, las pruebas utilizadas para seleccionar la estrategia de FL más eficaz podrían ampliarse utilizando conjuntos de datos más grandes y variando tanto el número de clientes como el número de rondas de agregación en la implementación. Además, la incorporación de trabajadores bizantinos garantizaría la solidez de la estrategia seleccionada. Otra posible vía para futuras investigaciones sería implementar el algoritmo desarrollado en un conjunto de FPGA para optimizarlo. Por último, el marco propuesto no tiene en cuenta las características de las FPGA, por lo que sería una línea de investigación interesante ampliar el modelo del cliente para incluir las características de la FPGA. De esta forma se podría analizar el impacto de la heterogeneidad de la plataforma.

Summary

Introduction

The deployment of Field Programmable Gate Array-based (FPGA-based) computing nodes across the processing infrastructure known as edge–cloud continuum enhances computational efficiency and energy savings compared to the use of CPUs and GPUs. These systems integrate specialized accelerators with general purpose processors, offering high flexibility and performance. However, they also introduce challenges in workload management, since tasks arrive dynamically and cannot be optimized during design time. To address this, resource management infrastructures must adapt models in real time while tracking both tasks and node characteristics.

This work is enclosed within European research project MYRTUS, which aims to create a reference framework for continuum computing that seamlessly integrates cloud, fog, and edge resources. The framework combines an AI-driven orchestration engine to optimize performance, energy efficiency, and security, with a unified design environment for cross-layer modeling, analysis, and automated code generation.

MYRTUS focuses on reconfigurable computing — systems, often FPGA-based, that can dynamically adapt their hardware for specific workloads using dynamic or partial reconfiguration — and the cloud-edge continuum, which enables the flexible deployment of applications across centralized clouds and distributed edge devices. This approach allows low-latency processing, real-time decision-making, and optimized performance, energy usage, and responsiveness across the entire computing spectrum.

Juan Encinas et al. (2025) proposed an incremental learning approach using Hoeffding adaptive regression trees (HART) to predict power and performance of accelerators deployed on dynamically reconfigurable FPGAs under such scenarios, ensuring low runtime overhead but requiring frequent retraining on individual devices. This thesis builds on that foundation by exploring alternative machine learning models within a Federated Learning (FL) framework. FL allows devices to collaboratively improve models across different platforms without sharing raw data, reducing retraining frequency and promoting knowledge transfer across nodes.

The main goals of this thesis are:

1. To evaluate ML architectures suitable for FL integration.
2. To analyze different FL aggregation strategies.
3. To implement FL with heterogeneous client workloads and assess system-level behavior.

Methodology

The framework proposed in this thesis was fully implemented in Python, making use of two key libraries: Keras, to construct, train, and evaluate deep learning models, and Flower, to simulate FL environments. The workflow was divided into two major stages. In the first stage, different machine learning models with potential for FL integration were studied and optimized. This was achieved through grid search procedures, in which models were trained incrementally and their performance was analyzed using Pareto front diagrams to balance prediction error and computational cost. Once the most effective architectures had been identified, the second stage involved implementing an FL program that trained three distributed clients, where each client represents the model deployed on an FPGA. In this phase, a wide range of aggregation strategies were tested, and their

inference performance was evaluated to determine the most suitable approaches for dynamic workload prediction.

Three model families were investigated in detail: Regression Function Models using a Self-adaptive Differential Evolution (SaDE) optimizer, Dense Neural Networks (DNNs), and Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs). Three regression functions were studied: Linear function, Rosenbrock function and Rastrigin function. SaDE is a variant of classical evolutionary optimization that integrates adaptive control parameters and probabilistic selection of mutation strategies to enhance robustness. Its strength lies in reducing manual parameter tuning and adapting dynamically to historical performance. In this work, the SaDE framework was implemented using multiple mutation and crossover strategies.

DNNs were explored as a more scalable alternative. These feedforward architectures were tested in two configurations: two-layer and three-layer models. A comprehensive grid search was conducted, varying the number of neurons in each layer and the batch sizes during training.

The third family of models studied were LSTMs, recurrent neural networks specifically designed to capture temporal dependencies in sequential data. LSTM cells incorporate forget, input, and output gates to regulate information flow and mitigate the vanishing gradient problem. Several variants were tested, including pure LSTM layer, LSTM with one or two additional dense layers, and hybrid configurations combining a one-dimensional convolutional layer with LSTMs. As with the DNNs, a grid search over hyperparameters such as the number of units, dense layer sizes, kernel sizes, and batch sizes was performed.

The evaluation of all models relied on five key metrics: mean prediction error, error standard deviation, mean error deviation, inference time per data point, and total training time. These metrics were visualized through Pareto front diagrams, allowing a multi-dimensional assessment of each model's performance. The most critical trade-off involved minimizing mean error while maintaining acceptable total computational time. This approach ensured that model selection was based not only on accuracy but also on practical constraints such as runtime efficiency.

Once the best-performing models had been identified, the thesis advanced to the federated learning stage. The *Federated Learning* database was subdivided into three independent workloads, one per client, allowing each FPGA to account for and adapt to the varying characteristics of the underlying data distributions. Subsequently, the three models are merged into a single server-side model that aggregates the characteristics from all of them. A 10-fold cross-validation was then performed on each subset, training each client on 9 folds of their respective database and then testing both the clients and the server on a unified evaluation set consisting of the remaining fold of each subset.

A total of twelve aggregation strategies were studied to assess their effectiveness under heterogeneous conditions. The baseline algorithm, FedAvg, performed simple weighted averaging of client updates but was known to be sensitive to non-IID data, stragglers, and adversarial attacks. To address these limitations, adaptive optimization methods such as FedAdagrad, FedAdam, and FedYogi were tested, each incorporating different strategies to adjust learning rates and stabilize convergence. Momentum-based approaches like FedAvgM and the more general FedOpt framework introduced server-side optimizers to further improve training dynamics. Robust aggregation techniques, including FedMedian, FedTrimmedAvg, Krum/Multi-Krum, Fault-Tolerant-FedAvg, and Bulyan, were

examined for their ability to mitigate the effects of Byzantine clients or outliers. Finally, FedProx was evaluated as a method to stabilize training on heterogeneous data by penalizing updates that diverge significantly from the global model.

Results

The regression function models demonstrated poor predictive capacity, with mean absolute percentage errors (MAPE) consistently exceeding acceptable thresholds. Its stochastic nature and sensitivity to parameter tuning made it unreliable for dynamic workload prediction. Similarly, LSTMs, despite their theoretical ability to capture sequential dependencies, produced unstable results and higher error deviations. Their computational overhead further limited their suitability for deployment on FPGA-based systems.

In contrast, DNNs emerged as the most effective solution. Across both two-layer and three-layer architectures, they consistently achieved lower error rates, particularly for power prediction tasks, with MAPE often below 5%. Importantly, two-layer DNNs outperformed deeper ones, balancing predictive accuracy with reduced training and inference times, as presented by Summary Table 1 below. This efficiency made them ideal candidates for integration into federated learning simulations. Although DNNs did not always outperform the baseline HART models, the ability to apply FL on them outweighed that fact.

The second stage of experiments evaluated twelve aggregation strategies using the *Federated Learning* database, with three clients trained under heterogeneous workload partitions. The models were incrementally updated at each client, aggregated at the server, and then tested against a combined evaluation set.

Summary Table 1: Best models using DNNs

	Model	Mean error (%)	Sdv error (%)	Mean Error Dev. (%)	Total train time (s)	Individual infer time (s)
Top Power	FL 36 SL 24 BS 50	4.314	3.434	0.081	3.467	0.694
	FL 35 SL 25 TL 10 BS 25	4.089	3.266	0.066	4.690	0.755
	Baseline HART	2.772	4.681	0.1331	28.088	0.027
Bottom Power	FL 24 SL 8 BS 25	3.876	3.458	0.575	4.354	0.745
	FL 30 SL 30 TL 10 BS 25	3.325	3.162	0.040	6.240	0.983
	Baseline HART	2.017	3.952	0.2202	28.56	0.024
Time	FL 32 SL 12 BS 1	27.579	28.957	0.219	93.778	0.798
	FL 35 SL 25 TL 10 BS 1	26.695	27.934	0.565	130.844	1.035
	Baseline Ensemble HART	27.076	40.301	3.818	404.147	0.108

Note: FL = First Layer, SL = Second Layer, TL = Third Layer, BS = Batch Size; Best models highlighted in green

The results showed that one of the three metrics (consumed time by aggregation step) was negligible when compared to the other two. Furthermore, the exceptional effectiveness of specific strategies depending on the output variable were proven. For CPU power (Top Power) prediction, FedMedian delivered the best performance, for FPGA power (Bottom Power) prediction, FedProx1 proved to be the most robust, effectively handling workload heterogeneity. For execution time, Bulyan consistently outperformed other strategies.

Conclusions and future research lines

The experiments confirmed the usefulness of DNNs for system inference, with two-layer architectures performing better than three-layer ones by reducing training and inference times, though with a slight increase in error. Batch size 1 was found to be practical only for execution time models, as it caused excessive training times for power models. While

overall accuracy was slightly lower than the one of the previously used baseline models, the ability to integrate federated learning compensated for this difference.

Federated learning strategy results showed that aggregation time was negligible and differences between strategies were minimal. Variability across runs was also negligible for CPU and FPGA power models, though more noticeable for execution time. Based on the evaluation, the most effective strategies identified were FedMedian for CPU power models, FedProx1 for FPGA power models, and Bulyan for execution time models.

Finally, this work suggests several avenues for future research. Firstly, the results of our framework could be applied to other FL strategies in addition to those already coded in Flower. Secondly, the tests used to select the most effective FL strategy could be expanded by utilizing larger datasets and varying the number of clients and aggregation rounds in the implementation. Adding byzantine workers would ensure the robustness of the selected strategy. Another possible avenue for future research would be to implement the developed algorithm in a set of FPGAs to optimize it. Finally, the proposed framework does not take into account FPGA characteristics. An interesting area for future research would be to expand the client model to account for FPGA characteristics and platform heterogeneity.

List of Acronyms

AI: Artificial Intelligence

ANN: Artificial Neural Network

ARTICO³: Arquitectura Reconfigurable para el Tratamiento Inteligente de Cómputo, Consumo y Confiabilidad

CNN: Convolutional Neural Network

CPU: Central Processing Unit

DE: Differential Evolution

DL: Deep Learning

DMA: Direct Memory Access

DNN: Dense Neural Network

FL: Federated Learning

FPGA: Field-Programmable Gate Array

FSM: Finite State Machine

HART: Hoeffding Adaptive Regression Tree

IoT: Internet of Things

GPU: Graphics Processing Unit

HPC: High-Performance Computing

Non-IID: Non-Independent and Identically Distributed

LSTM: Long-Short Term Memory

MAPE: Mean Absolute Percentage Error

ML: Machine Learning

NN: Neural Network

ReLU: Rectified Linear Unit

RFM: Regression Function Model

SaDE: Self-adaptive Differential Evolution

Sdv: Standard Deviation

SoC: System-on-Chip

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Deploying Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)-based computing nodes across the edge–cloud continuum enhances computational efficiency by integrating application-specific hardware accelerators with hard-/soft-core processors. In particular, reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems built on commercial FPGAs offer exceptional flexibility and performance while delivering significantly higher energy efficiency than equivalent Central Processing Units (CPUs) or Graphics Processing Units (GPUs).

However, this also introduces new challenges in resource management, in addition to existing ones such as reconfiguration management and software-to-hardware computation offloading. Workload orchestration in the edge–cloud continuum often creates highly dynamic scenarios, where tasks may arrive at any time and be assigned to any available resource. As a result, node-specific workloads can no longer be represented as static task graphs that are easily scheduled and managed at design time. To efficiently handle these dynamic workloads, resource management infrastructures must maintain accurate knowledge of both the tasks and the characteristics of each node.

This work is enclosed within a European research project MYRTUS [1] “Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems” (Grant Agreement: 101135183). The main goal of this project is to establish a reference continuum computing framework – a system that enables the seamless deployment and management of applications across a continuous spectrum of computing resources – that integrates cloud (centralized, high capacity servers), fog (regional or local intermediate nodes) and edge resources (devices close to data sources or end users) to support complex, dynamic cyber-physical systems. It combines an AI-driven runtime orchestration engine to optimize performance, energy efficiency and security, with a unified design and programming environment that enables cross-layer modelling, analysis, design space exploration and automated code generation.

The MYRTUS project focuses around two main ideas, reconfigurable computing and cloud-edge continuum. Reconfigurable computing [2] refers to computational systems that can dynamically modify their hardware configuration to adapt to specific application requirements. Unlike traditional fixed-architecture processors, reconfigurable systems, which are often based on FPGAs, allow custom hardware pipelines, parallelism and specialized processing units to be configured on demand.

Reconfigurable systems can be classified according to two distinct criteria: the scope of reconfiguration (partial or total) and the timing (static or dynamic). Static reconfiguration requires stopping the device, whereas dynamic reconfiguration can occur during system operation without execution being halted. However, not all combinations are meaningful: for example, a fully dynamic reconfiguration of the entire device is impractical. The most relevant approach and the one that will be applied in this study, is partial dynamic reconfiguration, which allows selected regions of the hardware to be modified while the rest of the system continues running. This differs from the typical use of FPGAs, where static and total reconfiguration is standard, essentially replacing the entire bitstream whenever the hardware is reprogrammed. On the other hand, partial dynamic reconfiguration enables more flexible systems and opens new possibilities for optimized performance, energy efficiency and responsiveness across a variety of workloads, from signal processing to machine learning.

Cloud-edge continuum [3] describes a seamless integration of computing resources, spanning from centralized cloud data centres to distributed edge devices located near data sources. In this continuum, cloud resources provide scalable computation, large-scale

storage and advanced analytics capabilities. On the other end, edge devices enable low-latency processing, real-time decision-making and efficient bandwidth utilization. By orchestrating workloads dynamically across cloud, fog and edge layers, cloud-edge continuum frameworks reap the benefits of both, optimizing the performance, energy consumption and responsiveness of applications while maintaining flexibility and reliability across the entire computing spectrum.

Researchers at the Centre for Industrial Electronics and Multimodal Systems (CEIMM) presented an infrastructure [4] to support run-time model updates by incremental learning mechanisms to perform power consumption and performance predictions on FPGA-based workloads. Specifically, a Hoeffding Adaptive Regression Tree (HART) [5] was selected to predict FPGA power consumption and execution time of a given workload, leveraging its ability to use drift detectors to monitor and replace branches when accuracy decreases. These models are trained from performance traces acquired during previous execution of different combinations of tasks. For predicting performance, an ensemble of those HART trees [6] was modelled to address the higher prediction complexity, as grouping several instances of learners created a stronger learner than the individual ones.

This Master Thesis extends that baseline infrastructure published in [4] by studying alternative Machine Learning (ML) models that are suitable for applying Federated Learning (FL). While the current incremental learning mechanism ensures low run-time overheads during the (re)training stage, the ability to share learning curves between different devices would prove beneficial for the system. This advantage becomes even more significant in a cloud-edge continuum, where, unlike the current system in which each node learns only from tasks it has performed, a federated learning (FL) approach would allow every node to benefit from the experiences of all nodes across the continuum. In this regard, the impact on execution performance on the board is limited as the adaptive incremental learning process will remain the same, retraining when signs of model degradation appear and stopping when model accuracy is stable. Furthermore, the use of federated learning would decrease the number of times that a given FPGA has to retrain its model as it would have also learned from the workloads other boards have encountered. Figure 1 shows the proposed framework of this Master Thesis:

Figure 1: Master Thesis Framework

Note: Results are highlighted in green.

The entire framework of this master's thesis is hosted and maintained in a GitHub [7] repository (<https://github.com/des-cei/IncNN-DW> [8]). GitHub is a web-based platform that supports version control and collaborative software development using Git, a distributed control system. It enables developers and researchers to host, manage and track changes to source code and related files over time. Furthermore, it provides tools for collaboration such as issue tracking, pull requests, code review, etc. which facilitate coordinated work among individuals and teams. As a result, it is widely used in both academic and industrial contexts for developing, sharing, and maintaining software projects.

1.1 Motivation

The increasing deployment of FPGA-based computing nodes across the edge–cloud continuum has highlighted their potential for accelerating applications with high performance and energy efficiency. However, the dynamic nature of workloads in such distributed environments introduces significant challenges in terms of modelling and resource management. Traditional approaches, which rely on static task graphs or centralized retraining, are not well suited for scenarios where tasks arrive unpredictably and must be allocated to heterogeneous nodes.

Previous research has demonstrated the feasibility of using incremental learning techniques to update predictive models of FPGA power consumption and execution time at runtime. While effective, this approach requires frequent retraining on each individual device, which limits scalability and increases overhead. The absence of knowledge sharing between nodes further constrains the adaptability of such systems.

These limitations motivate the exploration of alternative machine learning approaches capable of maintaining high prediction accuracy while enabling distributed model training. In particular, Federated Learning offers a promising solution, as it allows multiple devices to collaboratively improve their models without centralizing sensitive workload data. Investigating the integration of lightweight yet effective ML models into a federated setting thus becomes essential to address the challenges of dynamic workload characterization in FPGA-based systems.

1.2 Main Goals

The main goals of this Master Thesis are listed below:

- Research different on alternative ML models for representing the behaviour of reconfigurable systems under dynamic workloads and optimize these for integration in FL frameworks.
- Study and develop different FL strategies to aggregate the selected machine learning model.
- Develop an experimental framework to evaluate the behaviour of a FL system with different workloads per client to study the server model response.

1.3 Alignment with Sustainable Development Goals

This Master Thesis lays the groundwork for developing a task scheduler capable of finding the optimal task sequence to reduce both power and time consumption when presented with a set of tasks to perform. Although when considering a single FPGA is a small save up, if applied to a great number of FPGA across the world, both the social (due to time save) and environmental (due to energy save) impact would be massive. Due to this fact, this Master Thesis would contribute to two Sustainable Development Goals. Firstly, to goal 9, Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, as it is an innovative framework that can have a great economic impact both on efficiency and cost cuts. On the other hand, it helps indirectly to goal 13, Climate Action, as when performed at a large scale, energy

save up would mean less energy needed to be produced which could come from non-renewable energy sources.

1.4 Document Structure

This Master Thesis has been organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 briefly discusses the different tools used in this paper.
- Chapter 3 presents a survey of different techniques developed to address the problems associated with modelling dynamic workloads on edge devices and applying FL on them.
- Chapter 4 discusses the methodology proposed in this paper.
- Chapter 5 compares the performance of the models proposed in this Master Thesis and presents the results obtained when applying FL.
- Chapter 6 concludes and presents future research lines.

Chapter 2: Background

2.1 Reconfigurable Computing Architectures

Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are reconfigurable integrated circuits that can be programmed by the user after manufacturing to implement custom digital hardware functionalities. FPGAs provide a high degree of flexibility, allowing the hardware architecture to be tailored to the specific application. This makes them particularly suitable for applications that demand high performance, low latency, and parallel processing capabilities [9].

An FPGA comprises an array of configurable logic blocks, which typically includes look-up tables, flip-flops and multiplexers. These can be configured to implement both combinational and sequential logic. It also contains a programmable interconnection network, that enables complex digital systems to be created by allowing flexible routing between logic blocks. An FPGA architecture is completed with memory, digital signal processing and input/output blocks. Due to these characteristics, FPGAs are widely used in domains such as digital signal processing, telecommunications, embedded systems, and hardware acceleration. A diagram of an FPGA structure is presented below:

Figure 2: FPGA structure [10]

A System-on-Chip (SoC) is an integrated circuit that incorporates multiple components of a complete computing system within a single chip, such as processors, memory interfaces, peripherals, and communication modules. In FPGA-based platforms, SoCs often combine a processing system, commonly based on general-purpose processors, with programmable logic on the same device. This integration enables tight coupling between software execution and custom hardware implementations, allowing designers to distribute system functionality between software running on the processor and hardware accelerators implemented in the programmable fabric [11].

This heterogeneous architecture offers key significant advantages in terms of performance and energy efficiency. Software components benefit from the flexibility and ease of development provided by processors, while computationally intensive or time-critical tasks can be offloaded to hardware accelerators in the FPGA fabric. As a result,

FPGA-based SoCs are well suited for embedded and real-time applications that require both adaptability and high computational efficiency.

A key feature of FPGAs is their ability to be reconfigured, meaning that the functionality implemented in the hardware can be modified by loading a configuration bitstream. Reconfiguration can occur during system initialization, where the entire device is configured, or dynamically during operation. Many modern FPGAs support partial reconfiguration, which allows specific regions of the programmable logic to be reconfigured while the remainder of the system continues to operate without interruption. The capability for reconfiguration enables dynamic adaptation of hardware resources, improved utilization of the FPGA fabric, and post-deployment updates of hardware functionality. This makes reconfigurable computing a powerful approach for designing flexible and future-proof systems, particularly in applications where requirements may evolve over time or where multiple functionalities must be supported on a single hardware platform [12].

2.2 Baseline Infrastructure

Applying supervised machine learning to predict the behaviour of reconfigurable systems under dynamic workloads involves several steps: managing the changing workloads, coordinating the offloading of hardware acceleration requests to the FPGA fabric, and collecting power consumption and performance measurements from the FPGA-executed tasks. These measurements are then processed during the modelling phase and used to train the predictive models.

The study in [13] presents, validates, and evaluates an infrastructure called the workload manager, where multiple components operate in an integrated manner to address these challenges. The core principles of that work, which are organized into three main components: workload generation, workload offloading, and workload registration, will be described below.

2.2.1 Workload Generation

To apply a data-driven modelling algorithm, a sufficiently large dataset of the system's power and time consumption under different conditions is required to ensure the model performs correctly under unforeseen conditions. This dataset is obtained by a component that generates different workload patterns, producing a series of hardware-acceleration tasks that dynamically arrive at the system. This will generate n acceleration requests that arrive at a specific time, executing a specific kernel function.

2.2.2 Workload Offloading

This component handles all incoming hardware acceleration requests that make up the workload, whether generated by the previous component or originating from a real-world scenario, and determines their execution on the FPGA fabric based on a user-defined scheduling policy. To achieve this, a two-queue mechanism is employed: incoming jobs are first placed in a waiting queue, which is continuously monitored. Depending on the scheduling policy and the availability of hardware resources, requests are then moved to a scheduling queue, where they are configured onto the FPGA fabric using the ARTICo³ [14] framework, previously developed at CEIMM.

This framework (see Figure 3 below) is a run-time system designed to support dynamic and partially reconfigurable FPGA-based architectures in heterogeneous computing environments. It allows on-demand deployment, replication and removal of hardware accelerators, adapting the system at run time to varying application requirements, performance constraints, and reliability demands. ARTICo³ provides the necessary mechanism for dynamic resource management, such as accelerator scheduling, fault tolerance through hardware redundancy and performance scaling by adjusting the number

of accelerator replicas. By abstracting low-level FPGA reconfiguration and hardware management, the framework facilitates the integration of reconfigurable accelerators into larger software-defined and cloud-edge computing systems. This makes it particularly well-suited for real-time and adaptive workloads.

Figure 3: ARTICo³ Framework [14]

2.2.3 Workload Registration

This last component generates meaningful power consumption and performance traces of hardware-accelerated tasks using dedicated on- and off-chip monitors. These traces are later used as input to the ML-based models. The process records key information for each executed request — such as task identifier, arrival time, power consumption, and execution time — enabling the construction of a map that illustrates how the workload is executed on the FPGA fabric.

Most of this information is collected through the non-intrusive monitoring infrastructure illustrated in Figure 4. An external measurement board equipped with an Analog-to-Digital Converter (① in Figure 4) is used to capture power consumption data. This can be obtained either from USB-powered boards via an on-board shunt resistor, or from individual power rails through dedicated input ports connected to external shunt resistors. Data acquisition is performed through a Serial Peripheral Interface (② in Figure 4), supporting sampling rates of up to 1 Msample/s. In parallel, events from the internal digital signals of the hardware accelerators are recorded along with their timestamps (③ in Figure 4).

The monitoring process is orchestrated by a Finite State Machine (FSM) (④ in Figure 4), which coordinates the execution of all submodules based on queries from the control software running on the embedded processor (⑥ in Figure 4). A triggering module (also ④ in Figure 4) initiates the acquisition process according to a user-defined configuration. Once the internal Block RAMs reach capacity, a Direct Memory Access (DMA) engine (⑤ in Figure 4) transfers the collected traces to external memory. A typical operation

cycle includes: (i) trigger generation/detection, (ii) FSM-driven synchronization of power and performance trace acquisition, and (iii) DMA transfer of data to external memory.

Figure 4: Overview of the monitoring infrastructure [4].

Note: Blue blocks represent components of the monitoring infrastructure, (i) power traces acquisition components ((1) and (2)), (ii) performance acquisition components ((3)), (iii) infrastructure control components ((4) and (5)) and (iv) software drivers ((6)).

2.2.4 Modelling algorithm

As mentioned in the introduction section, this work extends the work of Encinas et al. [4]. The previous study developed three models in order to predict the power consumption of the processing system (hereafter referred to as Top Power, equivalent to the power consumption of element (6) in Figure 4), the power consumption of the programmable logic (hereafter referred to as Bottom Power, equivalent to the power consumption of elements (2) - (5) in Figure 4) and the time consumption when performing a given task (hereafter referred to as Time).

The model architecture employed for predicting Top Power and Bottom Power were HART [6], an incremental decision tree model that relies on the Hoeffding bound [15] to determine when a node should be split using a limited number of observations. This allows the model to learn efficiently from different data streams. Furthermore, incorporating drift detection enables the models to handle non-stationary environments, by adapting the tree structure in response to changes in data distribution.

On the other hand, an ensemble of HART predicted how long it would take to perform a given task. The reason behind using a different model lies behind the greater complexity required to correctly predict the time consumption compared to the power consumptions. This ensemble combines multiple HARTs to improve accuracy and robustness. By having each tree trained on different data samples and aggregating their outputs, this approach reduces variance and improves resilience

to noise and concept drift compared to a single model. However, this improvement comes at the cost of increased computational requirements.

2.3 Federated Learning

Federated Learning is a distributed machine learning technique that enables multiple clients (edge nodes, in this work, FPGAs) to collaboratively train a shared global model without transferring their local data to a central server. Instead of following the normal approach of centralizing raw data, each client trains locally on its dataset and transmits model updates to a coordinating server. This coordinating server then aggregates these updates following different strategies to refine the global model which is then subsequently redistributed to the clients for the next training round.

These techniques address common challenges in machine learning such as:

- Data privacy and security: as raw data never leaves the client device, it mitigates the risk associated with a central storage of sensitive information.
- Communication efficiency: since only model updates are exchanged, requirements are significantly reduced compared to transferring entire datasets.
- Scalability: FL can leverage massively distributed and heterogeneous data sources reflecting real-world data distributions. [16]

There are three main ways of aggregating models using FL:

2.3.1 Synchronous Aggregation

In this case, model aggregation occurs after every client update reaches the server, not considering the latency or potential delays experienced by individual clients. Some common synchronous FL algorithm are FedDyn [17], FedDist [18] and FedAAR [19]. Figure 5 illustrates the schematic diagram for synchronous aggregation.

Figure 5: Synchronous aggregation pipeline [20]

2.3.2 Asynchronous Aggregation

Asynchronous FL allows clients to upload their local updates in a staggered manner, which helps to mitigate the negative impact of device heterogeneity and delays produced by poor network or client crashes during training. Some asynchronous FL algorithm are FedPA [21], FedGKT [22] and Eiffel system [23]. Figure 6 illustrates the schematic diagram for asynchronous aggregation.

Figure 6: Asynchronous aggregation pipeline [20]

2.3.3 Semi-asynchronous Aggregation

Semi-asynchronous aggregation serves as a midway point between synchronous and asynchronous aggregation. These algorithms, like FedSA [24] or SAFA [25], optimize the trade-off between waiting time (synchronous) and resource consumption (due to communication / multiple updates – asynchronous).

2.4 Software

The framework of this work was developed using Python programming language and two open-source libraries, Keras [26] and Flower [27].

2.4.1 Keras

Keras is a high-level, open-source library written in Python that provides a user-friendly interface for designing, building and training machine learning and deep learning models. It manages much of the underlying complexity of frameworks like TensorFlow [28], allowing researchers to rapidly prototype models while maintaining flexibility for advanced customization. In this study, this library is used to build, train and infer Deep Neural Networks and Long-Short Term Memory models.

2.4.2 Flower

Flower is an open-source framework for federated learning. It enables researchers to train a different client on their respective datasets before aggregating them on a central server, without transferring the raw data. Flower provides a flexible and scalable infrastructure to coordinate training, aggregation and evaluation, allowing rapid modifications like changing the aggregation strategy, the number of clients to name two. In this Master Thesis, Flower was used to research the implementation of FL techniques and the performance of different aggregation strategies for modelling dynamic workload characterization.

Chapter 3: State of the Art

For the current work, the state of the art of two different subject areas was reviewed: successful cases of incremental characterization for dynamic workloads and the use of federated learning algorithms for dynamic workload characterization.

3.1 Incremental Characterization of Dynamic Workloads

When operating conditions fluctuate, systems must maintain real-time awareness of their state to adapt effectively to environmental changes. This requirement highlights a key limitation of static characterization. Incremental learning, on the other hand, provides a promising alternative by continuously training models throughout the system's operational lifetime. Its purpose is to counteract accuracy degradation in dynamic, real-world settings, thereby enabling effective runtime self-adaptation [29].

The core principles of incremental learning can be articulated as follows: model performance must remain robust in the face of evolving data distribution or dependencies typical of dynamic environments [30], and the model must assimilate new observations while preventing catastrophic forgetting, the unintended loss of previously acquired knowledge when encountering new data [31].

Current state-of-the-art research on incremental learning for workload characterization is predominantly focused on High-Performance Computing (HPC) applications running on resource-rich platforms. These systems can afford computationally intensive mechanisms, such as Neural Networks (NNs), to generate predictions. For instance, [32] introduces a framework to predict the power consumption of HPC jobs using a statically trained NN model. At runtime, predictions are compared against actual values; if discrepancies exceed a threshold, the model is retrained with new observations. Results demonstrate that this incremental approach effectively mitigates model drift and achieves higher accuracy than static models. In another example, [33] leverages a Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based NN to optimize energy-efficient resource allocation in multicore servers. The NN evaluates system configurations (e.g., number of cores, clock frequency, tasks per second), selects actions accordingly, and receives feedback based on energy consumption. Through exploration and exploitation, it adapts to runtime variations and significantly outperforms standard Linux governors in reducing power usage.

A comparable approach is proposed in [34] for Near-Memory Processing systems⁽¹⁾, where performance is improved by reducing communication overhead through dynamic data and computation remapping. Here, an RL agent with a Deep Neural Network (DNN) bases its decisions on system-level features such as page access rate and migration per access. Feedback is provided by a performance monitor embedded in the memory controller, which is used to update the RL agent via rewards. This method achieves substantial performance gains over baseline techniques. Finally, in cloud computing contexts, [35] highlights the limitations of traditional offline batch learning and adopts instead an incremental strategy to more effectively predict cloud task performance.

In contrast, comparatively little research has been conducted on resource-constrained platforms, which are commonly employed in edge computing scenarios. Existing approaches in this domain often rely on lightweight static solutions complemented by run-time updating mechanisms. For instance, the work in [36] addresses the reduction of GPU-induced power consumption in mobile processors by predicting the frame processing time of graphical workloads. Based on these predictions, the system selects the minimum GPU frequency required to satisfy performance constraints. To achieve this, the authors formulate a mathematical model describing variations in frame time and employ a Recursive Least Squares algorithm to update model parameters at run time,

⁽¹⁾: Near-Memory Processing (NMP) systems are architectures that place computation close to memory components to reduce data movement, thereby improving performance and energy efficiency for data-intensive workloads.

thereby adapting to workload fluctuations. The results demonstrate prediction accuracy comparable to static methods that depend on prior workload knowledge. Similarly, [37] proposes an approach for improving energy efficiency on heterogeneous platforms by combining design-time resource policies with run-time model training. In this framework, power consumption and performance models are trained online using hardware counters, and subsequently leveraged to adapt resource allocation policies to unseen applications. Experimental evaluations show that this strategy yields both reduced power consumption and faster execution compared to static techniques on heterogeneous architectures.

3.2 Federated Learning Applications for Characterizing Dynamic Workloads

Mali et al. [38] proposed a hybrid model that combines Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory and Gated Recurrent Unit layers with an attention mechanism to forecast resource utilization in Internet of Things (IoT) applications and predict dynamic task schedules at the client level. At the server level, they introduced an FL algorithm based on Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient, which aggregates the client models according to the resource availability of the user equipment. This combination of algorithms enabled optimized task allocation, improved performance, and reduced energy consumption.

To address the scalability challenges caused by the growing number of IoT devices, the Hierarchical Adaptive Federated Reinforcement Learning (HAFedRL) framework [39] was introduced. This framework employs a primal–dual update mechanism within a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient model at the edge level, facilitating efficient resource allocation and task scheduling under constrained edge resources. Furthermore, to ensure secure data aggregation while optimizing resource allocation, the authors proposed an Adaptive Multi-Objective Policy Gradient method at the central server.

Although Mali et al. [25] and the HAFedRL framework [26] provide important initial contributions in this domain, these are, to the best of our knowledge, the only two publications that directly address this specific topic. The scarcity of related work highlights the novelty of the field and indicates that it remains largely unexplored. Given the increasing relevance of efficient resource management and task scheduling in distributed and heterogeneous environments, further research is needed to expand on these early approaches, validate them in broader contexts, and explore alternative methods. Furthermore, both of them work on a cloud setting, meaning client training and inference are both performed on non-resource-constrained platforms, which enables them to use more complex algorithms. This makes the current work the first one to apply federated learning for dynamic workload characterization on resource-constrained platforms such as FPGAs.

Chapter 4: Description of the Proposed Solutions

The framework proposed in this work was fully developed in Python programming language using Keras [26] (to build, train, and infer DL models) and Flower [27] (to simulate FL on the best models) libraries. Therefore, this work is divided into two stages. On the first stage, different types of deep learning models applicable for FL were studied and optimized through a grid search program by incrementally training and testing the Model Selection dataset and plotting the results on Pareto front graphs. On the second stage, once the best model for each output was selected, an FL program was coded to train three clients on the FL dataset, testing different aggregation strategies. Finally, the inference performance of the different aggregation strategies was studied, and the best performing ones were selected.

4.1 Datasets

4.1.1 MachSuite Benchmark

MachSuite [40] is an open-source benchmarking suite designed to evaluate accelerators. It comprises a diverse set of compute- and memory-intensive kernels that are representative of workloads in the fields of embedded systems, signal processing, machine learning, and data analytics. This study investigates the behaviour of an FPGA fabric under data-intensive workloads by executing 11 of the MachSuite kernels using hardware accelerators instantiated on the device. For each instance, one or more kernels are evaluated at different degrees of parallelism by deploying 1, 2, 4 or 8 accelerators within the FPGA fabric. The 11 kernels under the scope of this project are [40]:

- AES: Implements the Advanced Encryption Standard, representing a computationally intensive cryptographic workload with a regular control flow.
- Bulk: Models bulk data transfer and accumulation operations, placing emphasis on memory bandwidth and streaming behaviour.
- CRS: Performs sparse matrix-vector multiplication using the Compressed Row Storage format, to highlight irregular memory access patterns.
- KMP: Implements the Knuth-Morris-Pratt string-matching algorithm, representing control-intensive pattern search workloads.
- KNN: Executes the k-nearest neighbours algorithm, capturing the distance computation and reduction patterns that are common in machine learning.
- Merge: Implements the merge step of merge sort, stressing data-dependent control flow and memory access.
- NW: Implements the Needleman-Wunsch algorithm for sequence alignment, representing dynamic programming with regular computation patterns.
- Queue: Models operations on a queue-based data structure, emphasizing pointer-based memory access and control dependencies.
- Stencil2D: Performs a two-dimensional stencil computation, representing structured grid-based numerical workloads.
- Stencil3D: Extends stencil computation to three dimensions, increasing computational intensity and memory reuse complexity.
- Strided: Models strided memory access patterns, stressing cache behaviour and memory subsystem efficiency.

4.1.2 Datasets Generated

Two datasets were generated using the MachSuite benchmark and the workload generation algorithm described in Section 2.1.1, each containing 15 numerical features and 3 outputs. Out of the 15 features, 11 of them represent the kernels described above

from the MachSuite benchmark, with the following possible values: 0 when the kernel is not executed; and 1, 2, 4 or 8 which represent the number of accelerators used to execute the kernel (it should be noted that there are only 8 accelerators in total). The three outputs correspond to the ones mentioned on Section 2.1.4: Top Power, which measures the power consumed by the processing system (CPU); Bottom Power, which measures the power consumed by the Programmable Logic (Monitoring IP + hardware accelerators); and Time, which represents the time taken to perform the given task. The number of data points and features, as well as the number of data points per part of each dataset are collected in Table I.

Table I: Summary of the two datasets

Dataset	Data points x features	Data points per part
Model Selection	98524 x 15	27177 / 34875 / 36490
Federated Learning	80875 x 15	26800 / 28766 / 25309

We divided each dataset into three parts (as shown in Table I above), based on which kernels from the benchmark were used. The first dataset was divided so that only the first 4, 8 or 11 kernels were executed in each part respectively. This dataset was used to train and select the best performing models without using FL techniques, studying both the error in stable and in changing conditions. For the second dataset, each part contained data points where only the first 4 (AES, bulk, CRS and KMP), from the 5th to the 8th (KNN, Merge, NW and Queue) or the last 3 (Stencil2D, Stencil3D and Strided) kernels from the benchmark were executed respectively. This dataset was used to apply FL techniques on the best performing models found with the first dataset.

4.2 Model Algorithm Selection

Three types of models were studied: Regression Function Models (RFM) [41], Dense Neural Networks (DNN) [42] and Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) [43]. These model architectures were selected because they have previously been successfully applied in federated learning studies. Additionally, they provide a diverse set of trade-offs: RFM are generally less computationally expensive, LSTM achieves exceptional results with sequential data, albeit at the cost of longer training times, and DNN represents a middle-ground option balancing performance and computational cost.

4.2.1 Regression Function Models

This work considers three regression models of increasing complexity in order to evaluate the optimization capabilities of the proposed approach. Each model defines a distinct objective function to be minimized, ranging from a simple linear formulation to highly non-linear and multimodal functions. The model parameters (the regression weights and bias term) are optimized using the Self-Adaptive Differential Evolution (SaDE) [44] algorithm, which allows for a systematic comparison of performance across different optimization landscapes.

- Linear function: the simplest possible function to study:

$$y = a_0 + a_1 \cdot x_1 + a_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + a_{15} \cdot x_{15} \quad (1)$$

- Rosenbrock function [45]: non-convex function commonly used in optimization challenges with strong variable interactions:

$$y = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{14} [100 \cdot (a_{i+1}x_{i+1} - a_i x_i^2)^2 + (1 - a_i x_i)^2] \quad (2)$$

- Rastrigin function [46]: multimodal function with many local minima commonly used to test the ability of the model to escape local minima and find global minima:

$$y = 10 \cdot 15 + a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{15} [(a_i x_i)^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi a_i x_i)] \quad (3)$$

where y is the predicted output, a_i is the weight associated with the i -th feature x_i and a_0 is a bias term that enables the function to shift vertically, thereby improving its fit to the data.

SaDE is an advanced variant of the classical Differential Evolution (DE) [47] algorithm, designed to improve robustness and reduce the need for manual parameter tuning. DE is a population-based stochastic optimization method that evolves a set of candidate solutions through iterative application of three processes: mutation, where a new mutant vector is created from the existing population; crossover, where it is decided at a component level whether to inherit from the target or the mutant; and selection, where the best-performing vector is chosen. This methodology is highly sensitive to the control parameters, such as the mutation factor and the crossover rate [48].

The SaDE framework addresses this by embedding the adaptation of control parameters and the strategy selection into the evolutionary process. Instead of relying on fixed settings, SaDE associates each solution with its own control parameters, which are adjusted dynamically based on historical performance. In addition, SaDE has multiple mutation strategies available, which are selected probabilistically according to success rates [44]. The general workflow of this algorithm is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: SaDE workflow [49]

Furthermore, three mutation strategies, two crossover strategies, and one selection strategy were studied:

- **Mutation strategies**
 - DE/rand/1 [50]: an exploration-oriented search that follows Equation (4) below.
 - DE/best/2 [51]: an exploitation-oriented search guided by the best solution as presented in Equation (5) below.
 - DE/current-to-best/2 [52]: balance between the exploration and exploitation oriented search following Equation (6) below.
- **Crossover strategies**

- Binomial crossover: most common strategy, where the CR parameter is adapted. This strategy is presented in Equation (7) below.
- Exponential crossover: crossover proceeds consecutively in dimensions instead of independently. The block length L depends on the varying CR parameter. Equation (8) presents this strategy below.
- Selection strategy \rightarrow SaDE always uses greedy selection [53], an algorithm based on survival of the fittest that follows Equation (9) below.

$$v_i = x_{r_1} + F \cdot (x_{r_2} - x_{r_3}) \quad (4)$$

$$v_i = x_{best} + F \cdot (x_{r_1} - x_{r_2}) + F \cdot (x_{r_3} - x_{r_4}) \quad (5)$$

$$v_i = x_i + F \cdot (x_{best} - x_i) + F \cdot (x_{r_1} - x_{r_2}) + F \cdot (x_{r_3} - x_{r_4}) \quad (6)$$

$$u_{i,j} = \begin{cases} v_{i,j} & \text{if } rand_j \leq CR \text{ or } j = j_{rand} \\ x_{i,j} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$u_{i,j} = \begin{cases} v_{i,j} & \text{if } j \in [j_{rand}, j_{rand} + L) \pmod{D} \\ x_{i,j} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$x_i^{g+1} = \begin{cases} u_i & \text{if } f(u_i) \leq f(x_i) \\ x_i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where x_i is the target vector at generation g , v_i is the mutated vector, u_i is the trial vector after crossover, x_{best} is the current best vector in the population, $x_{r_1}, x_{r_2}, x_{r_3}, x_{r_4}$ are randomly selected vectors different from x_i , D is the dimensionality of the problem, $F \in (0,2)$ is the mutation factor, $CR \in [0,1]$ is the crossover rate and j_{rand} is a randomly chosen index that ensures at least one dimension mutates.

4.2.2 Dense Neural Networks (DNN)

DNNs, also known as fully connected neural networks, are feedforward artificial neural networks in which each neuron (node) in a given layer is connected to every neuron in the subsequent layer. Formally, a dense layer computes its output as:

$$y = \varphi(Wx + b) \quad (10)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the input vector, $W \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is the weight matrix, $b \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the bias vector, $\varphi(\cdot)$ is a non-linear activation function and $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the output vector of the layer [54]. The activation function used in the present work is Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) [55] which computes its output as:

$$\varphi(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x \leq 0 \\ x & \text{for } x > 0 \end{cases} = \max(0, x) \quad (11)$$

Two DNN general architectures were studied, which are presented below.

Figure 8: General architecture of the DNNs studied

For these architectures, two grid-search [56] like algorithms were coded to train different hyperparameter combinations and select the best performing one. The search spaces for each model are presented in Table II below:

Table II: DNNs hyperparameters search space

Model	2-layered DNN	3-layered DNN
First layer n° of neurons	[36, 32, 28, 24, 20]	[35, 30, 25]
Second layer n° of neurons	[24, 20, 16, 12, 8]	[30, 25, 20]
Third layer n° of neurons	-	[20, 15, 10]
Batch size	[50, 25, 10, 1]	[50, 25, 1]
Number of combinations	100	81

The number of neurons in a layer defines the dimensionality of the layer’s representation and determines how many distinct features the network can learn at that stage. Each neuron learns a different weighted combination of the inputs, allowing the model to recognise complex patterns. Batch size is the number of training samples processed simultaneously before the model updates its parameters during training. It controls the trade-off between training stability and computational efficiency. While smaller batches provide more frequent updates (closer to incremental learning), larger batches enable more efficient use of hardware resources and more stable gradient estimates. Finally, the number of combinations indicates the number of possible hyperparameter configurations in the search space.

All DNNs modelled were coded using Keras [26]. In terms of configuration, the most commonly used optimizer, Adam [57], and bias initializer, zeros [58], were employed. In the case of weight initializers, the default initializer “glorot_uniform” was substituted by “RandomNormal” with the default values mean = 0.0 and stddev = 0.05. This was done due to the fact that “glorot_uniform” produces larger initial parameters, which tend to be further away from the optimal weight value when we take into account that the outputs are of the unit order.

4.2.3 Long Short Term Memory

LSTM is a recurrent neural network [59] architecture designed to address the vanishing and exploding gradient problems that hinder the learning of long-term dependencies in sequential data. This model incorporates a set of memory cells and gates to regulate the flow of information over time [43]:

- Forget gate (f_t): determines the information of the previous cell state to be discarded.
- Input gate (i_t): controls how much of the new information should be added to the cell state.
- Candidate cell state (\tilde{C}_t): potential update computed from the input and hidden state.
- Output gate (o_t): chooses which components of the updated cell state are exposed to the hidden state.

Formally, a LSTM cell updates at time step t as:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (12)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (13)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_c[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c) \quad (14)$$

$$C_t = f_t \odot C_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{C}_t \quad (15)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (16)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \quad (17)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid activation, $\tanh(\cdot)$ the hyperbolic tangent, \odot denotes element-wise multiplication, x_t is the input vector and h_t is the hidden state. A workflow of a LSTM cell is presented in Figure 9:

Figure 9: LSTM cell workflow

LSTM is a model architecture that can be easily combined with other models. Due to this, in this work, four different LSTM architectures are studied. First, is a basic one layer LSTM model. The second and third models include one or two dense layers (similarly to those used in DNN models above) added after the LSTM layer. Finally, the fourth model includes a 1-dimensional convolution layer (explained below) before the LSTM layer. These four structures are shown on Figure 10 below:

Figure 10: General architecture of the LSTMs studied

Convolution layers consist of learnable filters, known as “kernels”, which are small vectors of weights that transform the input vector using a mathematical operation called convolution. The convolution operation consists on sliding the kernel across the input vector and computing the scalar product between the filter weights and the local receptive field (a sub-region of the vector), producing a sequence of outputs values that form a new feature vector [60]. Each filter produces a different vector, responsible for capturing different patterns. It is worth noting that the generated vectors have lower dimensionality than the original one, as can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: 1-dimensional convolution operation

Following our approach with the DNNs, more grid-search [56] like algorithms were coded to train different hyperparameter combinations and select the best performing one. The search spaces for each architecture are presented in Table III below:

Table III: LSTMs hyperparameters search space

Model	Base LSTM	LSTM + Dense	LSTM + 2 Dense	1D conv + LSTM
N° of LSTM cells	[48, 32, 16, 8]	[32, 16, 8]	[32, 16, 8]	[32, 16, 8]
Dense layer 1 n° of neurons	-	[20, 16, 12]	[32, 28, 24]	-
Dense layer 2 n° of neurons	-	-	[24, 20, 16]	-
Kernel size of 1D conv layer	-	-	-	[2, 3, 5]
Batch size	[50, 25, 10, 1]	[50, 25, 10, 1]	[50, 25, 10, 1]	[50, 25, 10, 1]
N° of combinations	16	36	108	36

The number of LSTM cells in an LSTM layer corresponds to the number of memory units and defines the dimensionality of the hidden state. Similarly, the number of neurons in a dense layer defines the dimensionality of the layer’s representation, determining how many distinct features the network can learn at that stage. The kernel size specifies how many adjacent input elements are processed together by the convolution filter, thereby defining its receptive field. Batch size refers to the number of training samples processed simultaneously before the model updates its parameters during training. It controls the trade-off between training stability and computational efficiency. Finally, number of combinations indicates the number of possible hyperparameter configurations in the search space.

4.2.4 Model evaluation metrics

In order to identify the best hyperparameter combination of each model architecture, a model with every parameter combination within the space search was fitted and assessed using the first dataset. The method was performed five times to minimize the loss function, in the current case, Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):

$$MAPE_i = \left| \frac{Actual\ value_i - predicted\ value_i}{Actual\ value_i} \right| \cdot 100 \quad (18)$$

Then five different metrics were computed to select the best model. These metrics were:

- Mean error: After computing the mean error of each training iteration (not counting the first 1000 tests to avoid initial parameter error), the mean of the five iterations was calculated.

$$Mean\ error = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1000}^{Database\ Size} MAPE_j}{Database\ Size - 1000} \right)}{5} \quad (19)$$

- Sdv error: After computing the standard deviation of the error of each training iteration (not counting the first 1000 tests to avoid initial parameter error), the mean of the five iterations was calculated.

$$Standard\ deviation = \sqrt{\frac{1}{999} \sum_{i=1}^{1000} (MAPE_i - Mean\ error)^2} \quad (20)$$

- Mean error deviation: After computing the mean error of each training iteration (not counting the first 1000 tests to avoid initial parameter error), the standard deviation of the five iterations was calculated.

$$Mean\ error\ deviation = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 \left(\left(\frac{\sum_{j=1000}^{Database\ Size} MAPE_j}{Database\ Size - 1000} \right) - Mean\ error \right)^2}{5} \quad (21)$$

- Individual infer time: Defined as the time taken to infer an individual data point.

$$Individual\ infer\ time = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^5 (\sum_{j=1}^{Database\ Size} Infer\ time_j)}{5 \cdot Database\ Size} \quad (22)$$

- Total train time: Defined as the average time taken to train the whole dataset in each training iteration.

$$Total\ train\ time = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^5 \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\frac{Database\ Size}{Batch\ Size} + 1} Train\ time_j \right)}{5} \quad (23)$$

The reason why we compute *individual* infer time but decide to compute *total* train time, instead of *individual* train time, is due to the fact that, while we predict individual data points, training is performed with varying batch sizes. This means Individual train time is not a realistic metric, and Batch train time would prove harder to be compared as the bigger the batch, the longer that batch training would take. Due to this reason, it was decided to compute total train time as it was considered the most trustworthy metric.

With these five metrics, four Pareto front diagrams [61] would be plotted for each model type and algorithm:

- Sdv error vs Mean error
- Individual infer time vs Total train time
- Total time vs Mean error
- Total time vs Mean error deviation

Of the four, the third is the most important and should be optimized without compromising the others. It should be noticed that for 3 and 4, a new metric was created combining both times following Equation (24).

$$Total\ time = Individual\ infer\ time \cdot Database\ Size + Total\ train\ time \quad (24)$$

4.3 Implementation of the Federated learning Strategy

4.3.1 Benchmark preprocessing

In order to evaluate the performance of the different FL algorithms, the FL dataset was subdivided into three separate and independent workloads (as mentioned in section 4.1). Each new part would be used to incrementally train a client (a local model that is trained on its segment of the dataset that simulates the behaviour of FPGAs) in the FL implementation. Once the training of the clients has been completed, the server (global model generated with FL techniques, simulates the behaviour of a cloud server) will aggregate the models into one. All these models would then be saved and evaluated.

4.3.2 Implementation configuration

In order to implement the FL techniques to each model type (Top Power, Bottom Power and Time), a common configuration (.toml) file and three model-specific Python files are required. The configuration file contains general information of the program (such as library dependencies for simulation) and general configuration parameters (like batch size, learning rate, etc.).

Each of the remaining python files oversees the correct operation of a different element of the implementation. Firstly, the Server App file constructs the server model (simulating the behaviour of the cloud server) and defines the initial parameters of the clients, which aggregation technique will combine the clients to obtain the server weights, and how the server performance is evaluated. Similarly, the Client App code generates the necessary number of clients for the implementation. It then defines the behaviour of the clients, such as the conditions under which each client is trained and how they are evaluated. Finally, the purpose of the task file is twofold. On the one hand it defines the architecture of the DNN model generated by the client and server. On the other hand, it indicates to each client which part of the dataset they can access for training purposes.

Once flower implementations were performed successfully, a complete framework (Multi_Flower) for FL implementation was developed. This framework evaluates the performance of each FL strategy by implementing each one ten times. During each execution, both the client-side models and the aggregated server-side model are evaluated to assess their respective errors and aggregation times. Upon completion of the iterative process, the mean error, the standard deviation of the error and the mean aggregation time are computed to provide a measure of the accuracy, robustness and computational efficiency of each approach. All resulting metrics are stored in a structured dictionary, which is subsequently used to generate Pareto front graphs to facilitating comparative, multi-objective analysis of the federated learning strategies.

The complete implementation of the proposed framework, including all the necessary source code and configuration files, is publicly available on the following GitHub repository [8]. This repository provides full access to the developed framework and supports the reproducibility and further development of the work presented in this thesis.

4.3.3 Aggregation strategies

In this Master Thesis, a total of 12 different aggregation strategies available in the Flower library were studied. The chosen set of strategies cover a wide range of aggregation paradigms, including classical averaging, adaptive-optimization-based methods, momentum-enhanced approaches, robustness to stragglers and system failures, and defences against Byzantine or adversarial clients. This diversity enables aggregation behaviours to be assessed comparatively under heterogeneous and dynamic conditions. As such, this selection provides a representative and practical basis for exploring the impact of aggregation strategies in the developed models.

FedAvg

The Federated Averaging algorithm (FedAvg) [62] is considered the foundation for most federated learning methods. This algorithm iterates through the following steps until convergence:

- In each round t , the server selects a subset of clients S_t .
- The client k receives the global model ω_t and trains it locally on its dataset D_k for several epochs, obtaining an updated model ω_t^k .
- The server aggregates the updates, performing a weighted average where each client's contribution is proportional to the size of its dataset, as presented in Equation (25).

$$\omega_{t+1} = \sum_{k \in S_t} \left(\frac{|D_k|}{\sum_{j \in S_t} |D_j|} \cdot \omega_t^k \right) \quad (25)$$

This algorithm does have three main limitations:

- Non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) data problems [63]: arise when client data distributions differ significantly, the model may converge slowly or to a biased solution.
- Byzantine attacks [64]: Some clients may be faulty or malicious (called Byzantine workers). If they send corrupted updates, the global model can be degraded or manipulated.
- Stragglers [65]: Clients with slower computation or connection may bottleneck rounds.

Even with these limitations, this algorithm is still widely used as a baseline for comparison against more advanced algorithms.

FedAdagrad, FedAdam and FedYogi

To address the shortcomings of FedAvg, Reddi et al. (2021) [66] introduced FedAdagrad, FedAdam, and FedYogi as part of a unified framework for adaptive federated optimization.

FedAdagrad extends FedAvg by incorporating the Adagrad update rule into the server-side optimization step, that is:

- Client selection and training is the same as FedAvg
- Adagrad Update makes the server maintain a running sum of squared gradients, and the global model update is scaled per-coordinate. Adagrad rule follows Equations (26) and (27), where η is the global learning rate, ϵ is a small constant for stability and g_t is the weighted average of client updates.

$$v_t = v_{t-1} + g_t^2 \quad (26)$$

$$\omega_{t+1} = \omega_t - \eta \frac{g_t}{\sqrt{v_t} + \epsilon} \quad (27)$$

In centralized deep learning, Adam [57] is one of the most effective optimizers because it combines momentum with adaptive learning rates. FedAdam aims to adapt the Adam optimizer to the server-side of FL by modifying the server aggregation step. The new aggregation step is as follows:

- Maintain moving averages, as shown in the equations below:

$$m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) g_t \quad (28)$$

$$v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) g_t^2 \quad (29)$$

- Bias correction, presented in the equations below:

$$\widehat{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t} \quad (30)$$

$$\widehat{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t} \quad (31)$$

- Model update, that follows Equation (32):

$$\omega_{t+1} = \omega_t - \eta \frac{\widehat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\widehat{v}_t + \epsilon}} \quad (32)$$

While Adam is popular, it suffers from rapidly decaying learning rates due to accumulation of large, squared gradients. Yogi [67] was proposed to address this by controlling the growth of the adaptive accumulator in centralized learning. Later, [66] extended the idea to federated learning to stabilize training on heterogeneous data. FedYogi follows therefor the same process as FedAdam, changing Equation (33) to:

$$v_t = v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) \cdot \text{sign}(v_{t-1} - g_t^2) \cdot g_t^2 \quad (33)$$

FedAvgM

In centralized optimization, momentum [59] is a well-known algorithm that helps smooth gradient updates and accelerates convergence. Federated Averaging with Server Momentum (FedAvgM) [68] extends its predecessor by introducing server-side momentum during aggregation to stabilize learning under heterogeneity. It follows the iterative process below:

- Equal client selection and training as FedAvg.
- Server gradient estimates.

$$g_t = \sum_{k \in S_t} \left(\frac{|D_k|}{\sum_{j \in S_t} |D_j|} \cdot (\omega_t^k - \omega_t) \right) \quad (34)$$

- Momentum update at server with momentum coefficient $\mu \in [0,1)$.

$$v_t = \mu v_{t-1} + g_t \quad (35)$$

- Global model update.

$$\omega_{t+1} = \omega_t - \eta v_t \quad (36)$$

FedMedian

In adversarial or heterogeneous settings, just averaging client updates can significantly distort the global model. Federated Averaging with Median Aggregation (FedMedian) [69] modifies the aggregation step by using the coordinate-wise median instead of the mean, providing a simple yet effective robustness improvement. Therefore, the process follows FedAvg except for aggregating, where:

$$\omega_{t+1}[d] = \text{median}(\{\omega_t^k[d]: k \in S_t\}) \quad (37)$$

The new global model ω_{t+1} is formed by combining all coordinate-wise medians.

FedTrimmedAvg

Yin et al. [69] studied how fragile FedAvg is to outliers and Byzantine clients, developing FedTrimmedAvg, where they swap the mean for a coordinate-wise trimmed mean during server aggregation yielding a simple robustness boost. The aggregation step is presented below:

- For each coordinate d , collect $\{\omega_t^k[d]: k \in S_t\}$.
- Sort these values and remove the top f and bottom f values.
- Average the remaining $n - 2f$ values to obtain $\omega_{t+1}[d]$.

- Combine all coordinates into ω_{t+1} .

A condition to apply FedTrimmedAvg is that the total participating clients n and trimming level f must satisfy $n \geq 2f + 1$ (often, $n \geq 4f + 3$ is used for certain guarantees).

FedOpt

While investigating FL, researchers quickly realized that the server aggregation step can be seen as an optimization problem, not just simple averaging. This led to the FedOpt family [66] which provides a general framework where different server-side optimizers (Momentum, Adam...) can be plugged in. In other words, FedOpt provides a unifying framework for multiple algorithms by easily switching the server optimizer.

FedProx

FedProx [70] was proposed as an extension to FedAvg to stabilize training under heterogeneous (non-IID) settings by adding a proximal regularization term during local training. Instead of minimizing the loss function, in FedProx each client solves:

$$\min_{\omega} f_k(\omega) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\omega - \omega_t\|^2 \quad (38)$$

where $f_k(\omega)$ is the local loss on client k (MAPE in this work), ω_t is the current global model and $\mu \geq 0$ is the proximal coefficient controlling how tightly the client sticks to the model (higher μ means more conservative updates). In this Master Thesis, four values of μ were studied: 1, 0.1, 0.01 and 0.001.

Krum

FedMedian and FedTrimmedAvg improve FedAvg by acting per coordinate, but this means they ignore the geometry of full vectors. Krum and Multi-Krum [71] uses vector-level distances to select the update(s) most consistent with the majority, countering coordinated, high-dimensional attacks. Given n client updates $\{g^1, \dots, g^n\}$ and a Byzantine bound f , a step-by-step mechanism is presented below:

- For each client i , compute all pairwise squared distances $\|g^i - g^j\|^2$.
- For each client i , sort distances and sum the smallest $n - f - 2$; call this score $s(i)$.
- Krum: selects $i^* = \arg \min_i s(i)$, sets update as $g^* = g^{i^*}$.
- Multi-Krum: pick the best m indices with lowest $s(i)$ (without replacement) and set g^* as their average.
- Server updates global model with g^* .

To achieve theoretical robustness, the total participating clients n and trimming level f must satisfy $n \geq 2f + 3$.

Fault-Tolerant-FedAvg

The limitations mentioned before for FedAvg motivated Fault Tolerant FedAvg (FT-FedAvg) [72], which extends the original model to be more robust against faulty, unreliable or adversarial clients. FT-FedAvg modifies the aggregation step, instead of naively averaging all client updates, it introduces a fault-tolerant rule that detect and mitigate the influence of faulty updates, such as:

- Coordinate-wise Median [69]: Take the median value of each parameter across clients.
- Trimmed Mean [69]: Discards extreme values and average the rest.
- Krum / Multi-Krum [71]: Selects the update most consistent with others

With this modification it can tolerate up to $f < n/2$ faulty clients (depending on the aggregator).

Bulyan

The aggregation step where the server combines the updates of the clients is critical in federated learning. However, some clients may be faulty or malicious (Byzantine workers [64]). If they send corrupted updates, the global model can be degraded or manipulated. The Bulyan [73] strategy is an algorithm designed to mitigate Byzantine attacks better than classical aggregation rules.

Bulyan is a two-stage robust aggregation algorithm. First, a robust selection rule (such as Multi-Krum) is employed to iteratively select a set of “trusted” client updates. After, a coordinate-wise trimmed mean is applied to select a set, discarding the most extreme values for each model parameter before averaging. This enables Bulyan to identify reliable updates at the update level and reduce the effect of the outliers at the parameter level. To apply this strategy, the number of clients required is $n \geq 4f + 3$, which makes it computationally expensive.

Summary

A comparative table of the different FL strategies is presented below:

Table IV: Comparative table of Federated Learning Strategies

Strategy	Category	Main Idea	Strengths	Weaknesses / Limitations	Reference
FedAvg	Baseline	Clients perform local SDG; server weighted average updates	Simple Communication-efficient Widely used	Struggles with heterogeneous data Vulnerable to adversarial clients	[62]
FedAdagrad	Server Optimizer	Server applies Adagrad to aggregate updates + adaptive learning rate	Better adaptation to sparse gradients Improved stability	Can over-regularize Slower convergence in dense settings	[66]
FedAdam	Server Optimizer	Server applies Adam to aggregate updates + adaptive learning rate	Fast convergence Handles heterogeneous data better	More server hyperparameters Sensitive to tuning	[66]
FedYogi	Server Optimizer	Variant of Adam with controlled second-moment growth	More stable than Adam Mitigates exploding variance	Slightly slower adaptation than FedAdam	[66]
FedAvgM	Server Optimizer	FedAvg + server momentum	Stabilizes aggregation Helps with client drift	Adds another hyperparameter (momentum coefficient)	[68]
FedMedian	Robust Aggregation	Server uses coordinate-wise median instead of weighted mean	Byzantine/outlier robustness Simple to compute	Only coordinate-wise Ignores correlation Higher variance	[69]
FedTrimmedAvg	Robust Aggregation	Server trims top/bottom f values per coordinate, averages rest	Byzantine/outlier robustness Generalizes Median	Choice of f critical Ignores full-vector geometry	[69]
FedOpt	Meta-framework	General class using arbitrary server	Flexible	Needs tuning of optimizer-specific parameters	[66]

		optimizers (Adam, Adagrad, Yogi)	Unifies FedAvg and variants, adapts to heterogeneity		
FedProx	Heterogeneity (non-IID) Robustness	Adds proximal term to client objective → penalizes deviation from global model	Mitigates client drift Stable under non-IID data	Slower updates if proximal term too strong	[70]
Krum / Multi-Krum	Robust Aggregation	Selects update(s) closest to majority; average if Multi-Krum	Byzantine robust at vector level Accounts for geometry	Computationally expensive ($\mathcal{O}(n^2d)$) Discards many updates	[71]
Fault-Tolerant-FedAvg	Faulty Clients Tolerance	Extends FedAvg with mechanism for stragglers and client dropouts	More reliable in real-world (unreliable networks)	Slightly higher communication / coordination overhead	[72]
Bulyan	Robust Aggregation	Two steps: (1) robust selection rule (Multi-Krum); (2) coordinate-wise trimmed mean	Strong Byzantine resilience Combines geometry + coordinate robustness	Very computation-heavy Requires many clients ($n \geq 4f + 3$)	[73]

Note: Baseline = Foundation for most FL algorithm; Server Optimizer = Approaches enhance aggregation using server-side optimization techniques; Robust Aggregation = Aims to mitigate the impact of outliers or Byzantine clients; Heterogeneity Robustness = Addresses statistical heterogeneity across clients; Meta-framework = Develops general formulation to unify/extend multiple optimization strategies; Faulty Clients Tolerance = Handle stragglers and client dropouts

Chapter 5: Experimental Results

5.1 Baseline model

This study builds on the research presented in [4], adopting the proposed models as baseline references to evaluate the performance of the models developed in this thesis. In particular, the HART model and its extension, Ensemble HART, previously developed at CEIMM, are used as the baseline reference. HART is an incremental learning model designed to adapt to evolving data streams by updating its structure as new data become available, Ensemble HART, meanwhile, combines multiple HART learners to improve predictive performance and robustness through ensemble learning techniques.

Although the same model architectures are employed, the datasets used in this study differ from those considered in Encinas et Al (2025). Consequently, the numerical performance results cannot be directly compared with those previously reported, and the baseline models are trained from scratch within this study’s experimental setting.

To ensure a fair and consistent comparison, the baseline model is trained incrementally using the same training set as the proposed models and evaluated on the same testing set for each comparison. In the federated learning scenario, the baseline model is trained on the aggregated dataset comprising the training folds from all three clients and is then tested on the same final global test set. This provides a centralized reference against which the federated approaches can be assessed.

5.2 Model Architecture Selection

The first step is to research which of the machine learning model (among those explained in Section 4.2), can best model our accelerator characterization problem. To do this, a series of preliminary tests were performed, before applying a grid-search methodology to find the optimal combination of hyperparameters for that the selected model architecture. These preliminary tests were necessary carried out due to the high computational cost associated with exhaustive grid searches, so we avoid repeating the exhaustive search for all the potential models under evaluation. Model architectures that exhibited unsatisfactory performance in these preliminary evaluations were discarded, and grid searches were not performed for these configurations.

Due to the nature of the problem, it should be noted that every model is trained incrementally (one batch at a time with small batches, as predictions are sent in groups to avoid hogging the common bus) and tested incrementally (one data point at a time). Below, the results provided by the different architectures are presented:

5.2.1 Regression Function Models

The preliminary tests performed on the RFM consisted in training and testing the whole Model Selection dataset and computing the mean and standard deviation of the MAPE of the last 1000 predictions. This test was performed for every fitness function and starting with DE/current-to-best/2 and binomial crossover strategies. The best results for each model type of this preliminary tests are presented below:

Table V: Best preliminary results on RFM

Model Type	Mean MAPE (%)	Standard Deviation MAPE (%)
Top Power	25.3	12.4
Bottom Power	32.4	10.1
Time	79.3	40.3

Due to the poor classification results obtained on the preliminary tests, the conclusion that the ability to apply federated learning would not outweigh the increment in error was reached and, therefore, no more tests were needed to be carried out using this methodology.

5.2.2 Dense Neural Networks

DNNs were the only model that got over the preliminary tests and underwent the grid-search program. As mentioned in section 4.2.4, four pareto front diagrams per DNN architecture and model type were plotted (presented below). From these, we have arrived at the following conclusions:

- Models with batch size 1 tend to yield results with lower error at the expense of increasing training time considerably, when compared with other batch sizes.
- 3-layered models tend to yield results with lower error at the expense of increased training and testing time, when compared to 2-layered models.
- Top and Bottom Power models present lower errors and, therefore, lower test and train time are prioritized, however as Time models present higher errors, minimizing it is prioritized.

It should be noted that each pareto front contains three types of points: Pareto frontier points, No pareto frontier points and Selected Model. Furthermore, the selected model is always a Pareto frontier point from the third type of graph, Total time vs Mean error. This is due to the fact that, as was mentioned in Section 4.2.4, this is the most important out of the four graphs.

Figure 12: Pareto front graph - Sdv error vs Mean error - 2-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 13: Pareto front graph - Individual infer time vs Total train time - 2-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 14: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error - 2-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 15: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error deviation - 2-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 16: Pareto front graph - Sdv error vs Mean error - 2-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 17: Pareto front graph - Individual infer time vs Total train time - 2-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 18: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error - 2-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 19: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error deviation - 2-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 20: Pareto front graph - Sdv error vs Mean error - 2-layered DNN Time models

Figure 21: Pareto front graph - Individual infer time vs Total train time - 2-layered DNN Time models

Figure 22: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error - 2-layered DNN Time models

Figure 23: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error deviation - 2-layered DNN Time models

Figure 24: Pareto front graph - Sdv error vs Mean error - 3-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 25: Pareto front graph - Individual infer time vs Total train time - 3-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 26: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error - 3-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 27: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error deviation - 3-layered DNN Top Power models

Figure 28: Pareto front graph - Sdv error vs Mean error - 3-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 29: Pareto front graph - Individual infer time vs Total train time - 3-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 30: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error - 3-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 31: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error deviation - 3-layered DNN Bottom Power models

Figure 32: Pareto front graph - Sdv error vs Mean error - 3-layered DNN Time models

Figure 33: Pareto front graph - Individual infer time vs Total train time - 3-layered DNN Time models

Figure 34: Pareto front graph - Total time vs Mean error - 3-layered DNN Time models

Table VI below collects the results of the selected models on the pareto front diagrams above and compares them to the regression tree models used in [4]:

Table VI: Best models using DNNs

	Model	Mean error (%)	Sdv error (%)	Mean Error Dev. (%)	Total train time (s)	Individual infer time (ms)
Top Power	FL 36 SL 24 BS 50	4.314	3.434	0.081	3.467	0.694
	FL 35 SL 25 TL 10 BS 25	4.089	3.266	0.066	4.690	0.755
	Baseline HART	2.772	4.681	0.1331	28.088	0.027
Bottom Power	FL 24 SL 8 BS 25	3.876	3.458	0.575	4.354	0.745
	FL 30 SL 30 TL 10 BS 25	3.325	3.162	0.040	6.240	0.983
	Baseline HART	2.017	3.952	0.2202	28.56	0.024
Time	FL 32 SL 12 BS 1	27.579	28.957	0.219	93.778	0.798
	FL 35 SL 25 TL 10 BS 1	26.695	27.934	0.565	130.844	1.035
	Baseline Ensemble HART	27.076	40.301	3.818	404.147	0.108

Note: FL = First Layer, SL = Second Layer, TL = Third Layer, BS = Batch Size; Best models highlighted in green

Top and Bottom Power models presented such low errors (below 5%) that models with batch size different than 1 were considered optimal as increasing the error by around 2% decrease total time by around 100 seconds. On the other hand, Time models are on the opposite spectrum, in which choosing a batch size of 1 is optimal. This is due to the fact that choosing other batch size increases error by 20-30%, which was deemed unsustainable.

For all three model types, the best 2-layered DNN outperforms the 3-layered one, as the decrease in error is low enough that it is considered less valuable in comparison to the decrease in both training and inferring time provided by the 2-layered models. Although the baseline models outperform the selected Top and Bottom Power models, the difference is small enough that the ability of applying FL on them outweighs this fact.

5.2.3 Long Short Term Memory

The preliminary tests performed using LSTM consisted in training and testing the whole Model Selection dataset and computing the mean and standard deviation of the MAPE of the last 1000 predictions. This test was performed for each of the four model architectures described above taking into account that:

- This test was performed for each model type, each model architecture and each batch size.
- Four random parameter combinations from the search space on Table III were tested.

The results of these preliminary results were poor. Models that used batch size 1 would yield elevated errors as LSTM work best with big batch size where they can extract relationships between different data points. Furthermore, base LSTM results resulted computationally costly independently of the batch size (see Table VII below), making them unfeasible for the application at hand. As adding more layers would increase the computational cost, no more tests were needed to be carried out using this methodology.

Table VII: Best preliminary results using base LSTM

Model Type	Batch Size	Mean MAPE (%)	Standard Deviation (%)	Training Time (s)
Top Power	1	20.32	12.31	36.17
	Over 1	3.81	2.69	350.11
Bottom Power	1	19.13	14.76	35.21
	Over 1	3.58	2.23	327.43
Time	1	55.87	23.84	140.18
	Over 1	24.98	17.34	547.35

5.2.4 Model Selection and Final Modelling Architecture

A comparative evaluation of the three model architectures revealed clear differences in performance and computational efficiency. The RFM-based models exhibited poor predictive performance, characterized by high error values, which limits their suitability for the problem in question. While the LSTM-based models achieved competitive accuracy in some cases, their high computational cost and training complexity render them impractical for the subsequent experiments.

As a result, both the RFM and LSTM models are excluded from further analysis in this research. In contrast, the DNN-based models demonstrated a favourable balance between predictive performance and computational efficiency. Consequently, the DNN architecture has been selected for the next stage of this study. In particular, the best-performing DNN models, highlighted in green in Table VI, will be adopted and implemented using federated learning techniques in the following section, in order to find a federated solution for aggregating modelling knowledge across the continuum.

5.3 Federated Learning Results

In order to evaluate and select the best aggregation strategy from the ones described in section 4.3.3, a 10-fold cross-validation was performed for each strategy. Each of the three datasets for training the clients (section 4.3.1) were split into 10 equally sized subsets. After, each client would be trained with their respective dataset using 9 of the subsets, then the models would be aggregated into the server using the selected strategy. Afterwards, the weights of all four models are saved to be later evaluated on a new dataset formed by combining the unused fold from each dataset. This process would be iterated 10 times, each time using a different fold for testing. This methodology was employed to mitigate the bias of selecting a particularly good testing subset when performing traditional train-test split.

In order to evaluate each strategy, the mean and standard deviation error when predicting on the testing fold for each iteration was computed. Then the mean of those metrics across the five iterations was calculated. Also, the average time consumed by the aggregation step of each strategy were computed and are presented in Table VIII below:

Table VIII: Mean time consumed by the aggregation step of each FL strategy

Strategy	Average time consumed by aggregation step (ms)		
	Top Power models	Bottom Power models	Time models
FedAvg	3.518	3.046	3.256
FedAdagrad	1.870	1.832	1.728
FedAdam	2.627	2.652	2.616
FedYogi	2.507	2.777	2.675
FedAvgM	2.293	1.881	2.385
FedMedian	1.910	1.933	1.916
FedTrimmedAvg	2.404	2.638	2.614
FedOpt	2.063	1.895	2.018
FedProx $\mu = 1$	2.123	2.015	1.924
FedProx $\mu = 0.1$	1.967	2.010	1.859
FedProx $\mu = 0.01$	1.916	1.886	2.391
FedProx $\mu = 0.001$	2.024	1.885	2.406
Krum / Multi-Krum	1.961	1.895	2.081
Fault-Tolerant-FedAvg	2.625	2.576	2.479
Bulyan	2.262	1.919	2.224

The fastest strategy is therefore FedAdagrad, while the slowest one is FedAvg. Due to the significant difference between the aggregation times and the training/infering times, the relevance of this metric compared to the other two metrics was concluded.

To evaluate the best models' performance, four pareto front diagrams were plotted per model type. Each graph plots mean error vs standard deviation of the error across the five iterations when inferring with the server model on each workload type (kernel i for client's i dataset respectively) and the three combined (full test). These are presented below:

Figure 36: Pareto front graph – Full Test – FL strategy evaluation Top Power model

Figure 37: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 1–FL strategy evaluation Top Power model

Figure 38: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 2– FL strategy evaluation Top Power model

Figure 39: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 3 – FL strategy evaluation Top Power model

Figure 40: Pareto front graph – Full Test – FL strategy evaluation Bottom Power model

Figure 41: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 1– FL strategy evaluation Bottom Power model

Figure 42: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 2– FL strategy evaluation Bottom Power model

Figure 43: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 3 – FL strategy evaluation Bottom Power model

Figure 44: Pareto front graph – Full Test – FL strategy evaluation Time model

Figure 45: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 1– FL strategy evaluation Time model

Figure 46: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 2– FL strategy evaluation Time model

Figure 47: Pareto front graph – Kernel Type 3 – FL strategy evaluation Time model

When studying the pareto front graphs, it is clear that for Top and Bottom Power models, the standard deviation is negligible, as the worst case is below 0.2 and 0.8% respectively. Due to this, the strategies with the smallest mean error were selected as the best Pareto points, namely FedMedian for Top Power (lowest mean error on all Paretos). In the case of Bottom Power there is an 8-way tie between Fault-Tolerant-FedAvg, FedAvg, FedAvgM, FedOpt, FedProx1, FedProx0.1, FedProx0.01, and FedProx0.001, which have the same mean and standards deviation error up to 5 decimal places (3.52264% and 0.17248% respectively). FedProx1 was selected due to having the best results although as mentioned, the difference is negligible. Finally, in the case of Time models, the best strategy is Bulyan due to it containing the lowest Full test error with a low standard deviation. It also is one of the best performing strategies with every type of data.

It should be noted that some model’s results were not plotted due to their performance being much worse than other models, making the graph hard to interpret, namely:

- Top Power: FedAdagrad (Mean error \approx 1500%), FedAdam (Mean error \approx 600%) and FedYogi (Mean error \approx 80%).
- Bottom Power: FedAdagrad (Mean error \approx 1300%), FedAdam (Mean error \approx 600%) and FedYogi (Mean error \approx 80%).
- Time: FedYogi (Mean error \approx 100%) and Krum (Mean error \approx 200%).

These models tend to perform comparatively worse due to the nature of the test. As there is only one round, the aggregation step is carried out only once, leading these models that use an optimizer to perform worse than other strategies.

Table IX below compares the selected models on the pareto front diagrams with the original HART models trained on the whole FL dataset.

Table IX: Best Federated Learning Strategies vs baseline models

Model type	Strategy	Mean error (%)	Sdv error (%)	Aggregate Time (ms)
Top Power	Fed Median	5.083	0.070	1.910
	Baseline HART	2.373	2.868	---
Bottom Power	FedProx1	3.523	0.172	2.015
	Baseline HART	1.446	1.866	---
Time	Bulyan	57.977	4.705	2.224
	Baseline Ensemble HART	25.845	27.495	---

It should be noted that although the baseline models have lower mean error, the FL ones present lower standard deviation as well as reduced training times due to sharing the dataset among various clients. To ensure the aggregated model outperformed the clients, a final test comparing the performance of each client following the same approach as with the server was performed. In other words, this was a 10 k-fold cross-validation in which each client was trained separately on their respective dataset segment on each iteration, and then all of them were tested on the remaining fold. The results were added to the pareto graphs presented above, to facilitate a visual comparison for each workload type and the full test. These results are presented below:

Figure 48: Comparative graph – Full Test – Clients vs Server Top Power model

Figure 49: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 1 – Clients vs Server Top Power model

Figure 50: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 2 – Clients vs Server Top Power model

Figure 51: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 3 – Clients vs Server Top Power model

Figure 52: Comparative graph – Full Test – Clients vs Server Bottom Power model

Figure 53: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 1 – Clients vs Server Bottom Power model

Figure 54: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 2 – Clients vs Server Bottom Power model

Figure 55: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 3 – Clients vs Server Bottom Power model

Figure 56: Comparative graph – Full Test – Clients vs Server Time model

Figure 57: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 1 – Clients vs Server Time model

Figure 58: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 2 – Clients vs Server Time model

Figure 59: Comparative graph – Kernel Type 3 – Clients vs Server Time model

The Top Power comparative graphs show that the server models completely outperform the clients' models, as they present both lower mean and standard deviation errors. In the case of the Bottom Power models, the server models although they do not present the lowest mean error, the difference is small (around 0,1%) but they do present the lowest standard deviation, therefore they are still considered to outperform the clients' models.

In the case of the Time models are a case worth studying. The server models are without a doubt the best performing ones due to the low standard deviation (around half of the clients' models). That being said, it can be observed that these models do not perform well with Kernel Types 2 (KNN, Merge, MW and Queue, being the worst performing models) and Types 3 (Stencil2D, Stencil3D and Strided, which have middle performance). The reason behind them being the best performing models on the full test is due to the bigger errors encountered with Kernel Types 1, at which server models excel, off balancing their worse performance with other model types.

Finally, a comparative of the server model and the clients' models for the best FL strategy for each model type is provided below.

Table X: Comparative of Server vs clients for best FL strategy per model type

Model type		Full Test Mean ± Sdv error (% ± %)	Kernel 1 Mean ± Sdv error (% ± %)	Kernel 2 Mean ± Sdv error (% ± %)	Kernel 3 Mean ± Sdv error (% ± %)
Top Power	Server	5.083 ± 0.070	5.848 ± 0.099	5.488 ± 0.069	3.812 ± 0.088
	Client 1	5.808 ± 0.490	5.949 ± 0.299	6.411 ± 0.843	4.974 ± 0.833
	Client 2	5.686 ± 0.420	6.041 ± 0.306	6.087 ± 0.844	4.853 ± 0.708
	Client 3	5.423 ± 0.2453	6.197 ± 0.241	5.616 ± 0.514	4.384 ± 0.502
Bottom Power	Server	3.523 ± 0.172	2.478 ± 0.188	4.731 ± 0.274	3.255 ± 0.720
	Client 1	3.578 ± 0.458	2.559 ± 0.333	4.720 ± 1.032	3.360 ± 0.370
	Client 2	3.558 ± 0.502	2.387 ± 0.229	4.752 ± 1.111	3.443 ± 0.433
	Client 3	3.662 ± 0.367	2.294 ± 0.361	5.129 ± 0.860	3.443 ± 0.322
Time	Server	57.977 ± 4.705	63.961 ± 3.406	55.397 ± 5.208	54.324 ± 5.776
	Client 1	71.226 ± 43.345	123.34 ± 127.28	45.680 ± 15.110	45.069 ± 28.098
	Client 2	77.097 ± 41.676	134.85 ± 119.40	44.600 ± 14.173	52.876 ± 28.729
	Client 3	67.979 ± 37.85	106.54 ± 111.68	47.295 ± 14.305	50.691 ± 26.907

Note: Best results highlighted in green

Chapter 6: Conclusions and future work

The main objective of this work is to study the suitability and performance of FL strategies over centralized learning when representing the behaviour of reconfigurable systems under dynamic workloads. Under this objective, three Deep Learning models were implemented in this Master Thesis (RFM, DNNs, and LSTM) because they are reliable algorithms that have been used both for implementing FL and working under dynamic workloads.

Out of the three model architectures, two (RFM and LSTM) performed poorly, with high mean errors and/or high computational costs. On the other hand, this work proved the utility of using DNNs to analyse the system before applying FL techniques. Furthermore, the conclusion that 2-layered DNNs outperformed 3-layered ones, by reducing training and inferring time at the expense of a small increase in error was reached. Along this line, it can be observed that batch size 1 is only suitable for Time models, as the increase in training time is too large for the other model types. Results show that, although performance is slightly worse than the previously used HART models, the difference is small enough that the ability to apply FL techniques compensates it.

Results regarding the different FL strategies show that the aggregation time is negligible, both due to the short the aggregation step takes and the small difference there is between strategies. Furthermore, the standard deviation was also negligible for Top and Bottom Power models, as they are simpler to model than the Time models. With this in mind, the current best strategies for each model were selected: FedMedian for Top Power models, FedProx1 for Bottom Power models and Bulyan for Time models. The results also show that the aggregated models outperform those of the clients' models (specially for Top and Bottom Power models), as even for the Time models, where the data differs more between clients, the server models show improvement over the clients one.

Finally, this work suggests several avenues for future research. Firstly, the results of our framework could be applied to other FL strategies in addition to those already coded in Flower. Secondly, the tests used to select the most effective FL strategy could be expanded by utilizing larger datasets and varying the number of clients and aggregation rounds in the implementation. Adding byzantine workers would ensure the robustness of the selected strategy. Another possible avenue for future research would be to implement the developed algorithm in a set of FPGAs to optimize it. Finally, the proposed framework does not take into account FPGA characteristics. An interesting area for future research would be to expand the client model to account for FPGA characteristics and platform heterogeneity.

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Annex 1: Project Planning and Timeline

This annex presents the planning phase of the project, which defines the key tasks, their sequence, and the estimated duration required to complete them. Effective planning is essential to ensure that the project progresses in an organized manner and that resources are allocated efficiently. This project has been divided into nine tasks, which will be described now:

- Project planning and budget: This task includes defining the scope of the project and preparing a schedule and a budget
- Previous work research: This thesis is an extension of Juan Encinas et al. (2025) work. In order to carry this out the previous work had to be researched and understood.
- Federated learning research: Due to it being the most important concept of this work, federated learning had to be thoroughly researched.
- State of the art review: The literature was reviewed to study plausible solutions for this master's thesis.
- DL models testing: It consisted of testing different DL architectures and deciding whether they were suitable for the proposed framework.
- DL model evaluation: After selecting the suitable architectures, a grid-search program was coded to optimize different hyperparameters.
- Federated learning testing: Simulations on applying FL on the optimal models were carried out.
- Federated learning evaluation: This task consisted of a comparative evaluation of different federated strategies.
- Drafting of the master's thesis: In parallel to the other tasks, this document was drafted.

To visualize the schedule, a Gantt chart is presented below.

Figure 60: Gantt Diagram of project planning

Annex 2: Budget

1. Introduction

In the present document, we collect the different costs that the current framework carries. We will divide the costs into three sections: Software, Hardware, and Labor.

2. Software

Every software tool used in this master's thesis was open source, there was no real software expense.

3. Hardware

The hardware budget is collected in Table XI. It should be noted that the laptop computer used had upgraded RAM and ROM, therefore the prices of those components were included separately.

Table XI: Hardware budget

Hardware	Quantity		Price
Laptop	Base computer	1	691.71 €
	RAM	1	65.00 €
	ROM	1	100.00 €
Total:			856.71 €

NOTE: These prices may vary depending on retailer, location and any ongoing promotion and discounts. Additionally, embedded system prices are before tasks

Laptops tend to have a lifespan between 3-6 years, therefore 4.5 years will be used to obtain the depreciation of the laptop:

$$856.71 \cdot \frac{1}{4.5} = 190.38 \text{ €}$$

4. Labor

Algorithm adaptation of the developed framework may involve changes to the preprocessing, to the parameter settings, to the DL model architecture and the FL strategy; adjusting computational operations to optimize its execution taking advantage of hardware capabilities and testing to ensure correct operation. We assume a high knowledge to work with this, as time invested would depend on the abilities of the professional (engineer or software programmer) doing it. In any case, this process could take about 700 hours depending on the complexity of the dataset studied and the models generated, that could be paid at 15 € per hour (total range of 10500 €)

5. Total

Table XII collects the total budget of the current project. As the costs of each studied section can vary, the results collected will be given as a range of the plausible values.

Table XII: Total budget

Budget	Value	Time	Price
Software	0.00 €	---	0.00 €
Hardware	856.21 €	---	856.21 €
Labor	15.00 € / hour	700 hours	10500.00 €
Master Thesis Supervision Hours	50.00 € / hour	50 hours	2500.00 €
Total:			13856.21 €